

Multicomponent Ion Exchange Equilibria II. Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} - H^+ on Amberlite IR 120

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Binary and ternary ion exchange equilibria involving Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and H^+ ions have been studied by the batch technique, using the strong acid cation exchanger Amberlite IR 120. The ideal solid solution model of Argersinger *et al* has been used in the calculations of the thermodynamic equilibrium constants of the binary exchange equilibria; the specific ionic interactions in the solution phase insofar as these affect the corresponding ionic activities have been taken into account in the calculations. The mutual agreement of the ΔG° values of the three exchange reactions which together constitute a "triangle" has been discussed.

For the ternary exchange system the possibility of predicting ternary data by using the pair of binary exchange results containing the most preferred ion was examined. The graphical procedure suggested by Streat has been used, and the correlation between the experimental and the theoretically predicted results has been found to be good.

THE study of multi-ionic component selectivity and equilibrium data is essential for the development of ion exchange separation processes involving multi-ionic component mixtures. In view of the fact that the number of required experimental ion exchange equilibrium studies increases rapidly with each additional ionic component present, simple methods have been suggested for the interpolation of ternary and higher component data from a number of binary equilibrium results. Dranoff^{1,2}, Smith³, and Jasz and Lengyel⁴ proposed semi-empirical methods which ignored the effect of the presence of the third component on the binary equilibrium, while Soldatov *et al*⁵ attempted to take this into account by assuming the applicability of the Harned rule to the resin phase. Gopala Rao *et al*⁶ proposed a method of predicting weighted activity coefficient in the resin phase and observed that the use of the data for binary pairs containing the most favoured ion leads to the best prediction of ternary data. Streat *et al*⁷ examined the application of a simple empirical graphical extrapolation procedure for predicting ternary results from the corresponding 1-1 binary exchange data. For three component mixed valency systems, they proposed⁷ another empirical method, which has been discussed more fully in a recent communication describing the Zn^{2+} - Cd^{2+} - H^+ and Cu^{2+} - Ag^+ - H^+ systems⁸.

The object of the present study was to extend the investigation to the case of Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} - H^+ exchange system, on the same strong sulphonic acid type exchanger as had been used earlier. Though the component binaries Ca^{2+} - H^+ , Mg^{2+} - H^+ and Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} had been studied earlier in this laboratory⁹, it was considered desirable to reinvestigate these systems in view of the

fact that the reported Ca^{2+} - H^+ exchange showed an unusual type of variation of $\log K_a$ with the extent of resin loading by Ca^{2+} , and also because of the reported Mg^{2+} - H^+ exchange showing an apparent difference from the results reported by Bonner¹⁰. The ternary Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} - H^+ results have been analysed in terms of the method proposed by Streat.

Experimental

The binary cation exchange reactions Ca^{2+} - H^+ , Mg^{2+} - H^+ and Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} , and the ternary reaction Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} - H^+ were all studied on Amberlite IR 120 (PSSA, with 8% DVB). The Mg^{2+} - H^+ exchange was studied from both sides, starting from the pure Mg^{2+} as also H^+ forms of the resin; the Ca^{2+} - H^+ and Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} exchanges from the H^+ and Mg^{2+} forms of the resin respectively and, the ternary Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} - H^+ exchange from the H^+ form resin only. 0.25-0.30g moist resin, of known moisture content and exchange capacity[§], was allowed to react with 30 ml of the appropriate mixed electrolyte solution in pyrex bottles for 2-3 days with intermittent shaking at $25 \pm 2^\circ$. The concentrations of the cations in the equilibrium as also the starting solutions were determined analytically¹¹ [Mg^{2+} (as also total Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} in mixtures): EDTA, Erio T; Ca^{2+} : EDTA, HASSNA in 10 M KOH with known added Mg^{2+} in Ca^{2+} - H^+ mixtures]. The resin phase concentrations were obtained by difference. Stoichiometry of exchange was fully established in all the cases within limits of experimental error.

The resin used was of A.R. grade (Mallinckrodt). [Capacity, H^+ form: 4.79 meq/g (dry) for two different batches; Mg^{2+} form: 4.21 meq/g (dry),

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§ In the case of Mg^{2+} resin the capacity was determined both by repeated leaching with KNO_3 , as also by ashing; concordant results were obtained.

(shortfall on the basis of H⁺ resin capacity—7.65%]. HClO₄ and Mg(ClO₄)₂ used were G.R. (E. Merck); Ca(ClO₄)₂ was prepared from G.R. HClO₄ and A.R. CaCO₃¹².

Efforts were made to maintain the ionic strengths of the equilibrium solutions at 0.1 M but this was not always possible, particularly in the case of the unsymmetrical 2-1 exchanges. For Ca²⁺-H⁺ exchange μ=0.088-0.098, except in case of 4 exchanges (μ=0.074-0.087). For Mg²⁺-H⁺ exchange μ=0.086-0.106, except in case of 2 exchanges (μ=0.182 and 0.213). For Ca²⁺-Mg²⁺ exchange μ=0.100-0.106, except for 3 exchanges (μ=0.121-0.150). For the ternary Ca²⁺-Mg²⁺-H⁺ exchange, μ=0.116-0.120, except for 2 exchanges for which μ=0.103.

Calculations

For binary exchange between ions B^{p+} in resin and A^{q+} in solution, viz, pAX_q + qBRes_p ⇌ pARes_q + qBX_p, the equilibrium constant is :

$$K = \frac{(N_{AResq})^p (M_{Bp})^q}{(N_{BResp})^q (M_{Aq})^p} \cdot \frac{f_{AResq}^{p(\gamma_{\pm BX_p})^{q(p+1)}}}{f_{BResp}^{q(\gamma_{\pm AX_q})^{p(q+1)}}$$

$$= K_a \frac{f_{AResq}^p}{f_{BResp}^q} \quad \dots (1)$$

where the N's and f's are respectively the resin phase concentrations (mole fractions) and activity coefficients; the M's and γ's are respectively the solution phase concentrations (g. ionic) of the exchanging ions and the mean activity coefficients of the corresponding electrolytes in solution and K_a is the value of the selectivity coefficient corrected for the solution phase activity coefficients only. The solution phase activity coefficients refer to the usual standard state. If the resin phase activity coefficients are referred to a standard state of the homoionic form of the resin in equilibrium with an infinitely dilute solution of the electrolyte involved in the exchange, then it has been shown¹³⁻¹⁵ that

$$\ln K = \int_0^1 \ln K_a dX_{AResq} \quad \dots (2)$$

where X_{AResq} is the equivalent fraction of the resin in the ARes_q form. The standard free energy change per equivalent of exchange is given by the familiar relation :

$$-\Delta G^\circ = \frac{1}{pq} RT \ln K = \frac{1}{pq} 2.303 RT \int_0^1 \log K_a dX_{AResq} \quad \dots (3)$$

The solution phase activity correction for the binary electrolyte mixtures was carried out through evaluation of Bronsted-Scatchard¹⁶, Guggenheim¹⁷ ionic interaction coefficients, B, according to the method described earlier^{9, 18-21}.

The resin phase activity coefficients of the two exchanging ions are given by the expressions^{13, 15, 22}:

$$Z_B \ln \bar{\gamma}_A = -(1 - X_{AResq}) \ln K_B^A + \int_0^1 \ln K_B^A dX_{AResq} \quad \dots (4)$$

and

$$Z_A \ln \bar{\gamma}_B = X_{AResq} \ln K_B^A - \int_0^1 \ln K_B^A dX_{AResq} \quad (5)$$

Results and Discussion

The variation of (i) the resin phase activity coefficients γ_i of the two exchanging ions**, and (ii) the log K_a values with the extent of resin loading by the preferred ion, are shown in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively for the three binary exchanges considered. The K values calculated by graphical integration (equation 2) together with the accompanying standard free energy change per equivalent of exchange are shown in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Activity coefficient of the resinate ions vs extent of loading of the resin phase by the preferred ion, for the Ca²⁺-H⁺, Mg²⁺-H⁺ and Ca²⁺-Mg²⁺ exchange systems (Amberlite IR 120).

** The γ_i values have been calculated by using the K_a values from the smooth "log K_a vs resin phase equivalent fraction of the preferred ion" plots, rather than by using the actual experimental K_a values.

Fig. 2. $\log K_a$ vs equivalent fraction of the preferred ion in the resin phase for the $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$, $\text{Mg}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$ and $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{Mg}^{2+}$ exchange systems (Amberlite IR 120).

TABLE 1—LOG K AND ΔG° VALUES (ON EQUIVALENT BASIS) OF $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$, $\text{Mg}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$ AND $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{Mg}^{2+}$ EXCHANGE REACTIONS IN AMBERLITE IR 120 ($25 \pm 2^\circ$)

Exchange	$\log K$	ΔG° (k cal/equiv.)
$\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$	0.585	0.813
$\text{Mg}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$	0.471	0.649
$\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{Mg}^{2+}$	0.223	0.307 (predicted : 0.164)

The graphical method of Streat⁷ has been used for the prediction of the ternary results, by making use of the data for the component binaries containing the most preferred ion (viz. $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$ and $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{Mg}^{2+}$). The method is illustrated by referring to a typical experimental result in the $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{Mg}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$ system. For prediction of the resin phase concentrations in equilibrium with the following representative solution phase concentration: $x_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}=0.125$, $x_{\text{Mg}^{2+}}=0.128$ and $x_{\text{H}^+}=0.747$,

(i) the effect of H^+ was first neglected and the ternary data reduced to the $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{Mg}^{2+}$ binary pair, thus $x_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*=(x_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}/x_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}+x_{\text{Mg}^{2+}})=0.125/(0.125+0.128)=0.495$;

(ii) from the binary $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{Mg}^{2+}$ data, the resin phase Ca^{2+} concentration $y_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*$ in equilibrium with the solution phase Ca^{2+} concentration $x_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*$ ($=0.495$), was determined: $y_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*=y_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}/(y_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}+y_{\text{Mg}^{2+}})=0.698$;

(iii) the point $y_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*=0.698$ was plotted on the axis B-C of a triangular equilibrium diagram (Fig. 3) and it was joined to the point A ($y_{\text{H}^+}=1$); the line

is the locus of all resin phase compositions in equilibrium with $x_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*=0.495$;

(iv) a similar procedure was followed for reducing the ternary data to the $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$ binary pair after neglecting the effect of Mg^{2+} : ($x_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*=0.144$).

Then for $x_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*=0.144$, the corresponding $y_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*$ in equilibrium with $x_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*$ as found from the $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$ data is $y_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*=0.812$. The point $y_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*=0.812$ i.e., $y_{\text{H}^+}^*=0.188$ was plotted on the axis C-A of the triangular equilibrium diagram and joined to the point B ($y_{\text{Mg}^{2+}}=1$). This is the locus of all resin phase compositions in equilibrium with $x_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}^*=0.144$. The point of intersection of this line with the other one obtained earlier [mentioned in (iii)] locates the ternary point on the diagram.

Fig. 3. Graphical representation and prediction of ternary experimental data for the $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{Mg}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$ exchange system on Amberlite IR 120 (○ experimental, ● predicted).

The complete ternary data for the $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{Mg}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$ system is given in Table 2 and shown plotted in Fig. 3.

As mentioned earlier, all the three binary exchanges reported here had been studied earlier in this laboratory. A comparison with the earlier findings is therefore pertinent.

The present $\text{Ca}^{2+}-\text{H}^+$ exchange result shows a smooth fall of the $\log K_a$ values (from 1.4 to 0.8) with increase in resin phase Ca^{2+} loading; the earlier result⁹ showed a maximum of $\log K_a$ at about 60% resin loading ($X_{\text{Ca}^{2+}} \sim 0.6$). We are inclined to attribute the error in the earlier result over the lower $X_{\text{Ca}^{2+}}$ range to experimental errors in determining the extremely minute solution phase Ca^{2+} concentrations involved ($\sim 0.0001 M$), using Eriochrome Black T with added known quantity of Mg^{2+} . In the present study HASSNA indicator was used and measurements over $X_{\text{Ca}^{2+}} < 0.2$ were not attempted.

TABLE 2—Ca²⁺—Mg²⁺—H⁺ EXCHANGE
EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF H⁺ FORM RESIN = 4.762 MEQ/G (DRY) ; MOISTURE CONTENT 48.51% ; TEMPERATURE 25 ± 1°

Equivalent fractions of ions in solution			Results calculated for binary exchanges by reducing ternary exchange data					Equivalent fractions of the ions in the resin phase					
X _{Ca²⁺}	X _{Mg²⁺}	X _{H⁺}	Ca ²⁺ —Mg ²⁺		Ca ²⁺ —H ⁺			Experimental			Predicted		
			X _{Ca²⁺} [*]	Y _{Ca²⁺} [*]	X _{Ca²⁺} ^{**}	Y _{Ca²⁺} ^{**}	Y _{Ca²⁺}	Y _{Mg²⁺}	Y _{H⁺}	Y _{Ca²⁺}	Y _{Mg²⁺}	Y _{H⁺}	
0.0997	0.4171	0.4831	0.193	0.370	0.171	0.835	0.370	0.557	0.073	0.345	0.585	0.070	
0.3428	0.1705	0.4867	0.668	0.825	0.413	0.943	0.8026	0.1406	0.5676	0.785	0.165	0.050	
0.2355	0.3148	0.4497	0.428	0.640	0.344	0.923	0.6238	0.3256	0.0505	0.610	0.340	0.050	
0.0424	0.2823	0.6753	0.130	0.275	0.059	0.700	0.2472	0.6162	0.1365	0.245	0.646	0.109	
0.0672	0.1867	0.7459	0.265	0.470	0.0286	0.610	0.402	0.4518	0.1461	0.360	0.410	0.230	
0.1254	0.1280	0.7466	0.495	0.698	0.144	0.812	0.6018	0.2706	0.1276	0.600	0.260	0.140	
0.2435	0.0768	0.6797	0.760	0.880	0.264	0.892	0.8031	0.097	0.0999	0.795	0.100	0.105	
0.0399	0.1010	0.8591	0.283	0.490	0.0443	0.665	0.3837	0.4187	0.1976	0.392	0.412	0.196	
0.0539	0.0906	0.8550	0.373	0.590	0.0593	0.710	0.4824	0.3223	0.1953	0.478	0.330	0.192	
0.7600	0.079	0.8450	0.490	0.695	0.0825	0.750	0.5766	0.2414	0.1821	0.564	0.248	0.188	

The Mg²⁺-H⁺ exchange results reported earlier⁹ showed an apparently large deviation from those reported by Bonner. This apparent anomaly is now seen (Fig. 4 ; curves 1 and 2) to be fully attributable to our having taken into consideration the solution phase activity correction. The deviation of the present Mg²⁺-H⁺ exchange results from those reported earlier (Fig. 4, curves 3 and 2, respectively) is however real, and very likely attributable to the present more stringent control of the equilibrium-solution ionic-strength.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the results obtained from the present study for the Mg²⁺—H⁺, H⁺—Mg²⁺ binary exchange systems with (i) those obtained earlier in this laboratory⁹ and (ii) those obtained by Bonner¹⁰.

The log K_a values reported earlier⁹ for the Ca²⁺-Mg²⁺ exchange are somewhat larger than those of the present study[†]. The thermodynamic consistency of the above binary exchange results can be ascertained from a consideration of the extent of

mutual compatibility of the corresponding ΔG° values. It is seen that though the present results lead to considerable improvement in this respect

Fig. 5. Experimental 'equivalent fraction of the preferred ion in the resin phase vs that in solution' for the Ca²⁺—H⁺, Ca²⁺—Mg²⁺ and Mg²⁺—H⁺ binary exchange systems, compared with the corresponding results predicted from the ternary Ca²⁺—Mg²⁺—H⁺ system.

† The earlier reported log K (and also the corresponding ΔG°) values calculated by graphical integration should actually have been double those reported, i.e., 0.358 and 0.492 k cal/equiv. respectively, because of a numerical valence factor error in the calculations. This numerical error in the reported log K and ΔG° values is also present in the case of the other 2-2 (Mn²⁺—Zn²⁺, Mn²⁺—Mg²⁺ and Zn²⁺—Mg²⁺)⁹ and 2-4 (Th⁴⁺—Ba²⁺)¹⁰ exchanges reported earlier; the correct values should actually be double those reported. Whereas, the purported similar correction¹⁰ for the CrO₄²⁻—SO₄²⁻ exchange was actually unnecessary, so that the corresponding log K and ΔG° values (0.483 and 0.666 k cal/equiv. respectively) as reported first were correct (cf. footnote p. 21 ; ref. 18).

(Table I) compared to those reported earlier, there still remains a small hiatus in the mutual compatibility of the ΔG° values.

Ternary exchange system : A comparison of the predicted ternary exchange results with those actually obtained experimentally for the Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} - H^+ system has been made in Fig. 3. Tails are drawn to show the extent of deviation of the experimental points from those predicted by the graphical method⁷. Due to the much higher resin selectivity for Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions in comparison to that for H^+ ions, the experimental points tend to cluster along the Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} axis of the triangular diagram.

The binary equilibrium data have also been calculated from the experimental ternary data, after neglecting the effect of the presence of the third ion, by the method of calculation detailed earlier and are shown along with the experimentally obtained binary data in Fig. 5. The Ca^{2+} - Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} - H^+ binaries reduced from ternary are found to be in much better agreement with those obtained experimentally than is the case with the Mg^{2+} - H^+ binary. This finding is in conformity with the result obtained earlier by other workers⁶ that the prediction of binary data for the pair not containing the most preferred ion will not be satisfactory.

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References

1. J. S. DRANOFF and L. LAPIDUS, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1957, 49, 1297.
2. J. L. PIERONI and J. S. DRANOFF, *AIChEJ.*, 1963, 9, 42.
3. S. E. SMITH, *Eng. Bull. Purdue Univ., Eng. Ext. Series*, 1968, 132, (Part 2), 932.
4. A. JASZ and T. LENGYEL, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. (Hung.)*, 1961, 27, 247; 1962, 33, 395; 1962, 34, 19.
5. V. S. SOLDATOV and V. A. BYCHKOVA, *Russ. J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, 44, 1297.
6. R. K. BAJPAI, A. K. GUPTA and M. GOPALA RAO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1973, 77, 1288.
7. W. J. BRIGNALL, A. K. GUPTA and M. STREAT, "Proceedings of the International Conference on Theory and Practice of Ion Exchange", Cambridge, England, July, 1976.
8. M. SENGUPTA and T. B. PAL, *Reactive Polymers* (in press)
9. M. SENGUPTA, A. K. CHAKRAVARTI, G. C. PAL and P. MUKHERJEE, *Ion Exchange and Membranes*, 1973, 1, 149.
10. O. D. BONNER and L. L. SMITH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, 61, 326.
11. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd Edn., Longmans Green and Co., London, 1962.
12. H. H. WILLARD and F. SMITH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 283.
13. W. J. ARGERSINGER, JR., A. W. DAVIDSON and O. D. BONNER, *Trans. Kansas. Acad. Sci.*, 1950, 53, 404.
14. G. L. GAINES and H. C. THOMAS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, 21, 714.
15. E. EKEDAHL, E. HOGFELDT and L. G. SILLEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1950, 4, 556.
16. G. SCATCHARD, *Chem. Rev.*, 1936, 19, 309.
17. E. A. GUGGENHEIM and J. C. TURGEON, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1955, 51, 747.
18. G. C. PAL, A. K. CHAKRAVARTI and M. SENGUPTA, *Ion Exchange and Membranes*, 1974, 2, 21.
19. M. SENGUPTA, A. K. CHAKRAVARTI, G. C. PAL and P. MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 675.
20. R. A. ROBINSON and V. E. BOWER, *J. Res. Natl. Bur. Std.*, 1966, A70, 313.
21. G. E. BOYD, F. VASLOW and S. LINDENBAUM, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, 71, 2214.
22. E. HOGFELDT, *Arkiv. Kemi.*, 1952, 5, 147.